

Date	Observation Summary	Tier	Center
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of IGF1MTOR reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to KU-0063794 .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTOR reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to BRD-K19103580 .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTOR reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to dexamethasone .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to AZD4547 .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to carboplatin .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to compound 1B .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to tivozanib .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to trametinib .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Sep 19, 2016	Differential dependency network analysis of MTORC1 MEDIATED SIGNALLING reveals that EIF4EBP1 is differentially active in cell lines sensitive to VU0155056 .	Tier 1	Translational Genomics Research Institute
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates Basal-like from other classes of PAM50 mRNA clusters in 402 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates ColonAdeno from other classes of histological type in 459 samples of colorectal adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates EndometrioidAdeno from other classes of histological type in 200 samples of uterine corpus endometrioid adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates ERpositive from other classes of breast cancer triple marker in 386 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates HER2-enriched from other classes of PAM50 mRNA clusters in 402 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates LumA from other classes of RPPA clusters BRCA in 390 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates LuminalA from other classes of PAM50 mRNA clusters in 402 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates LuminalA from other classes of PAM50 mRNA clusters in 402 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates Mesenchymal from other classes of gene expression subtype in 184 samples of glioblastoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates MSI from other classes of gastric molecular subtype in 255 samples of gastric adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates MSI from other classes of gastric molecular subtype in 255 samples of gastric adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates RectalAdeno from other classes of histological type in 459 samples of colorectal adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates the difference classes of clinical stage in 454 samples of conventional clear cell renal cell carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates the difference classes of msi status in 263 samples of gastric adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates the difference classes of t status in 454 samples of conventional clear cell renal cell carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates TripleNegative from other classes of breast cancer triple marker in 386 samples of invasive breast carcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University
Dec 10, 2015	EIF4EBP1 was identified as an indicator that delineates UterineSerousAdeno from other classes of histological type in 200 samples of uterine corpus endometrioid adenocarcinoma .	Tier 1	Stanford University